

ON THE IRREDUCIBILITY OF $\{-1, 0, 1\}$ -QUADRINOMIALS

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Abstract

Let $a > b > c > 0$ be integers, and let $\beta, \gamma, \delta \in \{-1, 1\}$. We give necessary and sufficient conditions, in terms of a, b and c , for the irreducibility of $f(x) = x^a + \beta x^b + \gamma x^c + \delta$ over \mathbb{Q} .

1. Introduction

Throughout this note we let $a > b > c > 0$ be integers; $\beta, \gamma, \delta \in \{-1, 1\}$; and $f(x) = x^a + \beta x^b + \gamma x^c + \delta$. Previous investigations into the irreducibility of $f(x)$ over \mathbb{Q} have focused mainly on the nature of the possible factors or zeros of $f(x)$. In particular, Ljunggren proved the following theorem in [2].

Theorem 1. [Ljunggren] *The polynomial $f(x)$ is reducible over \mathbb{Q} if and only if $f(\zeta) = 0$ for some root of unity ζ .*

In [2], Ljunggren actually indicated how $f(x)$ factors when it is reducible. His statement, however, was incorrect in that he overlooked several cases. Mills [3], still using the methods developed by Ljunggren, later published a correct version of the theorem. At the end of [2], Ljunggren stated correctly that if a, b and c are all odd, then $x^a + x^b + x^c + \delta$ is irreducible. He went on to mention that, in all cases, similar criteria for irreducibility could be straightforwardly determined using his methods, although, citing the tediousness of such a task, he did not provide them.

Recently, using a different and less arduous approach, Dubickas [1] has given sufficient conditions for the irreducibility of a larger class of the quadrinomials $f(x)$ in terms of the

exponents a, b and c . In addition to proving the condition stated by Ljunggren for $x^a + x^b + x^c + \delta$, Dubickas shows that if a and b are even, and c is odd, then $x^a + x^b + \gamma x^c + 1$ is irreducible. In this paper we use techniques similar to those of Dubickas to give both necessary and sufficient conditions, based solely on the exponents, for the irreducibility of all quadrinomials $f(x)$ over \mathbb{Q} . The proof of our result relies on Theorem 1 and Lemma 1.

Our Lemma 1 is equivalent to Lemma 1 in [1], where the proof is geometric in nature. Nonetheless, we provide a proof here since our proof is algebraic.

Lemma 1. [Dubickas] *Let z_1, z_2 and z_3 be complex numbers which lie on the unit circle, and suppose that $z_1 + z_2 + z_3 + 1 = 0$. Then $z_j = -1$ for some j .*

Proof. Since $\text{Im}(z_1) + \text{Im}(z_2) + \text{Im}(z_3) = 0$, we can assume, without loss of generality, that $\text{Im}(z_1)\text{Im}(z_2) \geq 0$. Because $0 \leq |\text{Re}(z_j)| \leq 1$ for each j , we also have that $(\text{Re}(z_1) + 1)(\text{Re}(z_2) + 1) \geq 0$. Now, note that $|1 + z_1 + z_2| = 1$. We can expand and rewrite this equation to get

$$(\text{Re}(z_1) + 1)(\text{Re}(z_2) + 1) + \text{Im}(z_1)\text{Im}(z_2) = 0.$$

Therefore, it follows that $\text{Im}(z_1)\text{Im}(z_2) = (\text{Re}(z_1) + 1)(\text{Re}(z_2) + 1) = 0$. Suppose that $\text{Im}(z_1) = 0$. Then $z_1 = \pm 1$. If $z_1 = -1$, we are done. If $z_1 = 1$, then $\text{Re}(z_2) = -1$, and consequently, $z_2 = -1$. Since the same argument can be used if $\text{Im}(z_2) = 0$, the proof is complete. □

2. The Main Result

We begin with some notation. Suppose that $\text{gcd}(a, b, c) = 2^k m$, where m is odd. Let $a' = a/2^k, b' = b/2^k$ and $c' = c/2^k$. Define $\bar{a} := \text{gcd}(a', b' - c')$. Similarly, define \bar{b} and \bar{c} .

Theorem 2. *The quadrinomial $f(x)$ is irreducible over \mathbb{Q} if and only if $f(x)$ satisfies one of the following sets of conditions.*

1. $(\beta, \gamma, \delta) = (1, 1, 1)$
 $\bar{a}\bar{b}\bar{c} \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$

2. $(\beta, \gamma, \delta) = (-1, 1, 1)$
 $b' - c' \not\equiv 0 \pmod{2\bar{a}}, b' \not\equiv 0 \pmod{2\bar{b}}, a' - b' \not\equiv 0 \pmod{2\bar{c}}$

3. $(\beta, \gamma, \delta) = (1, -1, 1)$
 $b' - c' \not\equiv 0 \pmod{2\bar{a}}, a' - c' \not\equiv 0 \pmod{2\bar{b}}, c' \not\equiv 0 \pmod{2\bar{c}}$

4. $(\beta, \gamma, \delta) = (1, 1, -1)$
 $a' \not\equiv 0 \pmod{2\bar{a}}, b' \not\equiv 0 \pmod{2\bar{b}}, c' \not\equiv 0 \pmod{2\bar{c}}$

5. $(\beta, \gamma, \delta) = (-1, -1, -1)$
 $a' \not\equiv 0 \pmod{2\bar{a}}, a' - c' \not\equiv 0 \pmod{2\bar{b}}, a' - b' \not\equiv 0 \pmod{2\bar{c}}$

Remark. It is easy to show that the case $(\beta, \gamma, \delta) = (1, 1, 1)$ can be rewritten in a somewhat more appealing manner as follows:

The polynomial $f(x) = x^a + x^b + x^c + 1$ is reducible over \mathbb{Q} if and only if exactly one of the integers a' , b' and c' is even.

Proof. First observe that $f(1) = 0$ for any other choice of (β, γ, δ) , so that then $f(x)$ is reducible.

Note that case (2) is transformed into case (3) by replacing $f(x)$ with its reciprocal, $x^a f(1/x)$. Similarly, case (4) is transformed into case (5) by replacing $f(x)$ with the negative of its reciprocal. Since $f(x)$ is irreducible if and only if $\pm x^a f(1/x)$ is irreducible, it suffices to prove cases (1), (2) and (4) to establish the theorem.

To prove the case $(\beta, \gamma, \delta) = (1, 1, 1)$, assume first that $f(x)$ is reducible. Then, by Theorem 1, we have that $f(\zeta) = 0$, where ζ is some root of unity. By Lemma 1, either ζ^a , ζ^b or ζ^c equals -1 . If $\zeta^a = -1$, then $\zeta^{b-c} = -1$. Thus,

$$(-1)^{a'} = (\zeta^{b-c})^{a'} = \left(\zeta^{2^k(b'-c')}\right)^{a'} = (\zeta^a)^{b'-c'} = (-1)^{b'-c'},$$

which implies that a' and $b' - c'$ have the same parity. Similarly, if $\zeta^b = -1$, or $\zeta^c = -1$, then b' and $a' - c'$, or c' and $a' - b'$, respectively, have the same parity. Therefore, in any case, since at least one of the integers a' , b' and c' is odd, we obtain that exactly one of a' , b' and c' is even, which finishes the proof in this direction.

Conversely, if exactly one of the integers a' , b' and c' is even, then, either $a' - b'$ and c' are both odd, or a' and $b' - c'$ are both odd. Consequently, $x^{2^k} + 1$ divides $f(x)$ in any situation, since

$$\begin{aligned} f(x) &= x^{2^k b'} \left(x^{2^k(a'-b')} + 1\right) + \left(x^{2^k c'} + 1\right) \\ &= \left(x^{2^k a'} + 1\right) + x^{2^k c'} \left(x^{2^k(b'-c')} + 1\right). \end{aligned}$$

We now examine case (2): $(\beta, \gamma, \delta) = (-1, 1, 1)$. First suppose that the conditions hold, but that $f(x)$ is reducible. From Theorem 1, we know that $f(\zeta) = 0$ for some root of

unity ζ . Invoking Lemma 1, suppose that $\zeta^a = -1$. Then $\zeta^{b-c} = 1$. Write $a' = 2^r m_1$ and $b' - c' = 2^s m_2$, where m_1 and m_2 are odd. If $s \leq r$, then

$$(-1)^{m_2} = (\zeta^a)^{m_2} = \left(\zeta^{2^k m_2}\right)^{a'} = \left(\zeta^{2^{k+s} m_2}\right)^{a'/2^s} = (\zeta^{b-c})^{a'/2^s} = 1,$$

which contradicts the fact that m_2 is odd. Hence, $r < s$. Then

$$2\bar{a} = 2 \cdot \gcd(a', b' - c') = 2^{r+1} \gcd(m_1, 2^{s-r} m_2).$$

Now, $b' - c'$ is divisible by both 2^{r+1} and $\gcd(m_1, 2^{s-r} m_2)$, and since they are of different parity, it follows that $b' - c'$ is divisible by their product $2\bar{a}$, which is a contradiction. The argument is similar if $\zeta^b = 1$ or $\zeta^c = -1$.

For the converse, first suppose that $b' \equiv 0 \pmod{2\bar{b}}$. Then b'/\bar{b} is even, and since b'/\bar{b} and $(a' - c')/\bar{b}$ are relatively prime, we have that $(a' - c')/\bar{b}$ is odd. Therefore, $x^{2^k \bar{b}} + 1$ divides $f(x)$ since

$$f(x) = x^{2^k c'} \left(x^{2^k(a'-c')} + 1\right) - \left(x^{2^k b'} - 1\right).$$

Similar arguments show that $f(x)$ is reducible if $a' - b'$ is divisible by $2\bar{c}$, or if $b' - c'$ is divisible by $2\bar{a}$.

We omit the proof of case (4) since it is similar to the proof of case (2). □

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